

Enhanced Efficiency for Propagation of *Phalaenopsis cornu-cervi* (Breda) Blume & Rchb. F. Using Trimmed Leaf Technique

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Abstract : The effects of thidiazuron (TDZ) and benzyladenine (BA) on protocorm-like bodies (PLBs) induction from leaf explants was investigated. It was found that TDZ was superior to BA. The highest percentage and number of PLBs per leaf explant at 30 and 5.3 respectively were obtained on ½ MS medium supplemented with 9µM TDZ. The regenerated plantlets were potted and acclimatized in the greenhouse. These plants grew well and developed into normal plants after 3 month of transplantation. The 100% survival of plantlets was achieved when planted on pots containing sphagnum moss.

Keywords : orchid, PLBs, sphagnum moss, thidiazuron

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